

Green Marketing in India: A Sustainable Prospective

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ABSTRACT

Acknowledging awareness on the numerous environmental related problems has led a shift in the way consumers assume about their life. Changes has been observed in consumer believes for a green lifestyle. People are now days actively trying to decrease their smash on the environment. Although, this is not extensive and is still enlarge. Business and organizations however have identified this revamp in consumer attitudes and are trying to acquire a fringe in the competitive market by exploiting the prospective in the area of green market. In the modern epoch of globalization, it has emerged as a challenge to keep the consumers in bend and even keep our natural environment safe and that is the biggest need of the time. Green marketing is an occurrence which has developed specific significance in the current market and has transpired as an important notion in India and in other locations of the developing and developed countries, and is considered as a crucial strategy of accelerating sustainable development and growth. This research paper emphasizing on concept, need and prominence of green marketing. Data for this research has been collected from various sources of evidence, in addition to, journals, books, websites and newspapers. It investigates the main affairs in affectation of green marketing enactment. The paper narrates the current Scenario of Indian market and traverses the provocations of green marketing.

Keywords: *Green Marketing, Environment, Traditional Marketing, Consumer, Marketer*

I. INTRODUCTION

First of all, environment and environment related hindrance, one of the reason why the green marketing

emerged. The American Marketing Association stated, green marketing is the marketing of products which are presumed to be environment friendly. Thus, green marketing initiated an extensive range of tasks, comprises of product upgradation, a changes in the production process, packaging changes, as well as modification in advertisement. Green marketing belongs to holistic marketing approach wherein the product, marketing consumption on disposal of products and services takes place in a format that is less harmful to the environment with increasing apprehension about the consequences of global warming, non-biodegradable solid waste, harmful smash of pollutants etc., both consumers and marketer are becoming more fragile to the need for moving into green products and services. Many people trust that green marketing refers to the advertisement and promotion of products with environmental attributes. words like phosphate free, refillable, recyclable, ozone friendly environment friendly are most of the things consumers commonly linked with green marketing. Green marketing is a golden goose. According to per Mr. J. Polonsky, green marketing can be recognized as, "All initiatives framed to create and facilitate any exchange intended to satisfy human obligations or wants such that satisfying of their needs and wants occur with minimum detrimental input on the national environment." Green marketing is also termed as environmental marketing/ecological marketing. As amenities are limited and human needs are undefined, it is crucial for the marketers to use the resources efficiently without misuse as well as to attain the organization's objective. So green marketing is inevitable. There is increasing interest among the consumers across the world regarding the preservation of the environment. Worldwide affirmations indicate

people are concerned about the environment and are changing their attitude. As an outcome of this, green marketing has emerged which elaborates the growing market for viable and socially responsible products and services. Now this has emerged as a new mantra for marketers to satisfy the needs of consumers and earn better yield.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Dande, Brahma M. (2011), R, The Economic Times, Mumbai, had written an article which elaborates that, Green Ventures India is a subservient of New York based asset management organization Green Ventures International. As per recent latter announcement a \$300 million India focused fund aimed at renewable energy products and supporting trading in carbon credits.

Alsmadi (2012) in his study observed that the environmental deportment of Jordanian consumers discloses a big level of environmental conscience. Unfortunately, this positive likelihood and priorities in the "green" produces did not appear to have any impact on the last decision, obviously because these consumers had a stronger belief in the traditional products and a small confidence in the green affirmation.

Donaldson (2010) in his research realized in the Great Britain that in common the ecological behavior of consumers changed drastically. This study emphasized the strong temperament of consumers in the recognized commercial brands and in the frail behavior referring to the "green" asserts, which was the main reason behind the consuming defeat to interpret their concerns beyond the environment in their conducts

Gurmeet kaur, Sanjay K. Jain (2014) in their paper of environmentalism which had fast emerged as a worldwide circumstances discussed business firms also have risen to the occasion and have started reacting to environmental threatening by practicing green marketing approach. Green consumerism has played a catalytic role in ushering corporate environmentalism and making business enterprise green marketing oriented. Based on the analyzed data collected through a field survey, the paper made an evaluation of the extent of environmental attitude, awareness, and behavior prevalent among consumers in India.

Juslin E, Karna, J & Hansen, (2013) found that proactive marketers are the most genuine people in the implementations of environmental marketing voluntarily and seeking competitive advantage by environmental friendliness. The outcomes also demonstrate that environmental marketing strategies green values, functions and structures are logically linked to each other as hypothesized according to the model of environmental marketing used to guide this research.

Oyewole, P. (2010) in his conduct shown a conceptual attachment among industrial ecology and green marketing. It argues for maximum realization of environmental justice in the exercise for green marketing. A research plan is ultimately suggested to conclude consumer's awareness of environmental justice, and their willingness to bear the costs concerned with it.

Prothero, A. & Fitchett, J.A. (2008) stated that greater ecological enlightenment can be established by capitalism trough using the features of commodity culture to further advancement environmental goals. Marketing not only has the prospective to grant to the establishment of more sustainable forms of society but, as a principle agent in the operation and spread of commodity communication, also has a considerable duty to do so.

Prothero, A. (2009) has written up numerous papers in 'Journal of Marketing Management' stretched on green marketing. This involves a citation of the need to review existing literature on green marketing, an empirical study of United States and Australian marketing managers, a explanation of what a green union look like in practice in Great Britain, ecotourism and denotation of green marketing.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

1. To understand the concept of green marketing.
2. To discover the significances and needs of green marketing.
3. To analyze the prospects and challenges of green marketing.
4. To investigate the current scenario of green marketing in India.

IV. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The study will make an awareness amongst consumer to make a decision towards products and services which are more environment friendly and avoidance

of non-green based products and services. Green marketing concept is widely used as a gimmick by the gigantic corporate houses in order to make a distinction in the consumer's point of view when it comes to major market decision.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This research is an exploratory research based on data collected from secondary sources i.e. Newspaper, Journal's research publications, Websites and other reliable sources.

VI. EVOLUTION OF GREEN MARKETING:

The Green marketing concept was firstly discussed in a seminar on —Ecological Marketing organized by American Marketing Association (AMA) in the year of 1975 and taken its place in the literature. The term green marketing came into existence in 1980s and early 1990s. The first motion of green marketing arises in the 1980s. The concrete milestone for the first waggle of green marketing came in the form of published books, both of which were termed Green Marketing. They were written by Ken Peattie (1992) in the United Kingdom and by Jacquelyn Ottman (1993) in the USA. According to Peattie (2001), the evolution of green marketing can be distinguished in three phases.

First phase was named as "**Ecological**" green marketing, and in this period of marketing era all marketing initiatives were concerned to help environmental related obstacles and provide solutions for environmental problems.

Second phase was based upon "**Environmental**" green marketing and the attention repositioned on clean technology that includes creation of innovative products, which take care of pollution and waste management.

Third phase was declared as "**Sustainable**" green marketing. It came into reality in the late 1990s and early 2000 linked with developing good quality products which can fulfil consumers' needs by concentrating on the performance, quality, convenience and pricing and in an environment friendly way.

Characteristics of Green Products: We can define green products by following measures:

- 1) Products which are genuinely grown.
- 2) Products those are reusable, recyclable and biodegradable.
- 3) Products comes with natural ingredients.
- 4) Products comprises of recycled contents and non-toxic chemical.
- 5) Products only contents under approved chemicals.
- 6) Products that does not harm or pollute the environment.
- 7) Products which will not be tested on animals.
- 8) Products that are packaged under eco-friendly techniques.

VII. WHY FIRMS USES GREEN MARKETING?

Most of the companies are venturing into green marketing because of the following reasons:

Opportunity

In India, approx. 25% consumers gives their preferences to those products which are environmental-friendly products, and around 28% may be recognized healthy conscious. Therefore, green marketers have multiple and fairly sizeable sections to focus on. Surf Excel washing powder which preserves water (promoted with the message—" save two buckets water daily") and the energy-saving LG consumers durables are illustrations of green marketing. We also have seen green buildings which are coherent in their energy uses, construction and water materials, and which decrease the impact on human health and the environment.

Social-Responsibility

Many firms have started experiencing that they must behave in an environment-friendly format. They trust both in attaining environmental intents as well as objectives based on profit making. The HSBC is emerged as the world's first bank to go carbon-neutral. Other examples involve Coca-Cola, which has spent in many recycling activities. Walt Disney World in Florida, US, has an ample waste management agenda and infrastructure in place.

Governmental-Pressure

Numerous regulations have been framed by the government to secure consumers and the society at large. The Govt. of India too has developed a structure of ratification to decrease the production of harmful goods and by products. These reduce the industry's production and consumers' consumption of injurious goods, including those malign to the

environment; for instance, the forbid of plastic bags in major Indian cities like Mumbai and Delhi.

Competitive-Pressure

Many firms take up green marketing initiatives to maintain their competitive edge. The green marketing inventiveness by niche companies such as Green & Black and Body Shop have stimulated several mainline competitors to follow suit.

Cost-Reduction

Elimination of harmful byproducts may lead to considerable cost savings. Sometimes firms create symbiotic relationship whereby the waste produced by one company is utilized by another company as an industrial input to produce other product in a cost effective manner. For instance, The Coca Cola, Nike Inc. And procter & Gamble uses bio plastic material for the conversion of anything from clothing to packaging.

VII. BENEFITS OF GREEN MARKETING:

Consumers now a days are becoming more responsive about the environment and are also becoming socialist. Thus, many companies are accountable to consumers' desire for environmentally non damaging and neutral products. Several companies want to have an early-mover advantage as they have to ultimately shift towards becoming green. few of the advantages of green marketing are,

- It ensures sustainability and long-term growth along with profitability.
- It retains money in the long run, initially the cost is high.
- It supports companies to market their products and services following the environment aspects in mind. It helps in approaching the new markets and enjoying competitive advantage.
- Employees also feel proud and responsible to be the part of an environmentally responsible company.

IX. PROBLEMS OF GREEN MARKETING:

Several organizations desire to move green, as an expanding number of consumers want to involve themselves with environmental-friendly products. Alongside, one also observed doubt among the consumers concerning the products. In specific, one usually finds suspicion regarding the reliability of green products. Therefore, to confirm consumer trust, marketers of green products need to be much more

explicit, and desist from breaching any law or standards pertaining to products or business practices.

X. FIVE GOLDEN RULES OF GREEN MARKETING:

1. **Know your Customer:** There should be a confirmation that the consumer cautious and concerned regarding the issues that your product attempts to address.
2. **Educating your customers:** It is not just an event of letting people know, whatever you're doing it should protect the environment, but also a discussion of letting them know why does it matters.
3. **Being Genuine & Transparent:** Convey that a) You are literally doing what you affirm to be doing in the green marketing movement and b) The part of your business approach are steady with whatever you are doing that's environment friendly.
4. **Re assure the Buyer:** Consumers must be ensured to believe that the product discharging the task, in this firm should not forgot product standard in the name of the habitat.
5. **Consider Your Pricing:** If you are imposing a superior price for your product and many environmentally preferable products charges more due to economies of scale and use of higher-quality components confirm those consumers can sustain the premium and feel it's utility.

XI. COUNTRIES RANKED ACCORDING TO THEIR RESPONSE LEVEL ON GREEN MARKETING RANK COUNTRIES:

RANK	COUNTRY
1	INDIA
2	UK
3	USA
4	THILAND
5	AUSTRALIA
6	CANADA
7	CHINA

Source: RobecoSam

Table:1

XII. GEEN MARKETING MIX

When commercial units introduce with new innovations i.e. product based on eco-friendly they can approach for new market, increase their market share and earn maximum profits. Just like 4 pcs of marketing mix green marketing can also come up with

four important green components, but they are slight different. They also comprise of three additional Ps, namely planet, People and profit. Given below are the 4 pcs of green marketing.

A. GREEN PRODUCT

The products need to be produced according to the derived need of consumers who all are looking for a list of products which are environment friendly. Products can be framed using the have to be developed depending on the needs of the customers who prefer environment friendly products. Products can be manufactured using recycled items or from used products. Recyclable and efficient products do not only save water, energy and money but also does not harm the environment. The duty of marketing people in product management includes product designer along with market driven tendency and customer's plea for green products elements like organic, green chemicals, local sourcing etc. For example, Nike has declared as the first shoe maker company deals with green marketing. It has designed a variety of shoes that assures it has reduced garbage and used environment-friendly substances.

B. GREEN PRICE

Green pricing takes into consideration the people, planet and profit in a way that takes care of the health of employees and communities and ensures efficient productivity. Value can be added to it by changing its appearance, functionality and through customization, etc. Wal Mart unveiled its first recyclable cloth shopping bag. IKEA started charging consumers when they opted for plastic bags and encouraged people to shop using its "Big Blue Bag".

C. GREEN PLACE

Green place is about managing logistics to cut down on transportation emissions, thereby in effect aiming at reducing the carbon footprint. For example, instead of marketing an imported mango juice in India it can be licensed for local production. This avoids shipping of the product from far away, thus reducing shipping

cost and more importantly, the consequent carbon emission by the ships and other modes of transport.

D. GREEN PROMOTION

Green promotion involves configuring the tools of promotion, such as advertising, marketing materials, signage, white papers, web sites, videos and presentations by keeping people, planet and profits in mind. British petroleum (BP) displays gas station which its sunflower motif and boasts of putting money into solar power. Indian Tobacco Company has introduced environmental-friendly papers and boards, which are free of elemental chlorine. Toyota is trying to push gas/electric hybrid technology into much of its product line. It is also making the single largest R&D investment in the every-elusive hydrogen car and promoting itself as the first eco-friendly car company. International business machines Corporation (IBM) has revealed a portfolio of green retail store technologies and services to help retailers improve energy efficiency in their IT operations. The center piece of this portfolio is the IBM SurePOS 700, a point-of-sale system that, according to IBM, reduces power consumption by 36% or more. We even see the names of retail outlets like "Reliance Fresh", Fresh@Namdhari Fresh and Desi, which while selling fresh vegetables and fruits, transmit an innate communication of green marketing.

Green marketer can attract customers on the basis of performance, money savings, health and convenience, or just plain environmental friendliness, so as to target a wide range of green consumers.

Consumer awareness can be created by spreading the message among consumers about the benefits of environmental-friendly products. Positing of profiles related to green marketing on social networks creates awareness within and across online peer groups. Marketing can also directly target the consumers through advertisements for product such as energy saving compact fluorescent lamps, the battery – powered Reva car, etc.

XIII. TRADITIONAL VS. GREEN MARKETING

Source: Research gate

Fig. 1

XIV. GREEN MARKETING INITIATIVES IN INDIA:

Companies are initiating the green marketing techniques to capture the marketing attainments and retain customers. Below is the list of Indian companies stated their green initiatives. Many companies in India are adopting green for capturing market opportunity of green marketing. Listed below are examples of some Indian companies which have taken a green initiative. This shows a devotion of firms, as part of their corporate social responsibility or otherwise, to do something different which are worthwhile in this regard.

Environment Management Policy of HCL within HCL Eco Safe. The objective under HCL Eco Safe is targeted at coherent environmental management mechanism into their business execution thereby securing the health, environment, and wellbeing of all its stakeholders. HCL pledging to produce products that are environment friendly in all facet and are free from dangerous chemicals.

Honda India launched its model Civic a Hybrid car. However, at beginning the company was felt problems to sell its units because of its high price. The company then decided to slash their price to INR 8 lacs, and within very short span of time more than 100 cars were sold quickly

IBM a multinational technology company is promoting green solutions to corporate data centers where energy cost is emerging as obstacles to grow and the expansion of their business with the commitments that the cost incurred in energy energy would be decrease by half.

Idea Cellular an Indian Telecom giant executed its national campaign 'Use Mobile, Save Paper'. The firm organized an oath to save paper and trees. In cities bus shelters, the company decorated with potted plants and tendril climbers to circulate the green messages to the public.

IndusInd Bank established the nation's first ATM operated with solar-power and therefore came up with an eco-savvy reforms in India in banking.

ITC has instigated a premium business Paper Kraft, which is eco-friendly. The Social initiative of ITC has greened over 82,0000 hectares of land.

India's enormous oil company Oil and Natural Gas Corporation Ltd (ONGC), has initiated Mokshada green crematorium, which prevents 60 to 70% of wood in cremation process and also reduces burning time per cremation.

Reva, a Bangalore based company became the first company to manufacture an electric car. Reva is

operating their business in countries like Spain, Greece, Ireland, UK, Cyprus, Norway and Belgium.

Wipro InfoTech has been emerged as India's first IT firm to introduce Computer peripheral which are environment friendly. In India the IT giant has launched a new variety of Laptops and desktop recognized as Greenware. These set of products are based upon RoHS (Restriction of Hazardous Substances) eliminating e-waste in the environment.

TOP GREEN COMPANIES IN INDIA 2016

Rank	Newsweek green score	Company	GIC Sector
151	56.1%	Tata Consultancy Services	Information Technology
185	52%	Infosys	Information Technology
351	27.2%	Housing Development Finance Corp	Financials
352	27.2%	Sun Pharmaceutical Industries	Health Care
357	26.4%	ITC	Consumer Staples
373	24.5%	Hindustan Unilever	Consumer Staples
437	17.7%	ICICI Bank	Financials
438	17.6%	Reliance Industries	Energy
445	17%	HDFC Bank	Financials
449	16.3%	State Bank of India	Financials

Source: Newsweek

Fig. 2

XV. THE PROSPECTIVE OF GREEN MARKETING:

Many ways are there to rightly understand the concept of green marketing and to avert green marketing myopia. The overall ideology is that a company always should come up with effective green products that satisfies today's desirous customers. The question still persist what are future prospects of green marketing.? Business experts have observed this as a "frill" discussion, providing that environmentalism's approval of restrictions and preservation does not mix well with marketing's conventional principles of "render customer what they need" and "sell as much

as you can". Affirmation confirms that victorious green products have eliminated green marketing myopia by following three essential principles:

Value Positioning of Consumers

- Design best suited products that are environment friendly and nonhazardous.
- Stimulate and supply green based products customers desired and also aim market segments for the relevant customers.
- Expand mainstream request by covering consumer required value into environmental products.

Enhancement of Consumer Knowledge

- Make awareness among consumers with marketing communication that attach environmental elements with desired consumer value.
- Frame product characteristics as “solutions” for consumer needs and want.
- Develop educational websites which educates customers about environmental products and their benefits to the environment.

Reliability of Product Claim

- Employ benefits to the consumers and develop environmental products that are specific and meaningful.
- Secure product recommendations or eco-certifications from reliable third parties and inculcate consumers regarding the significance behind those eco certifications and endorsements.
- Uplift consumer support via consumer’s internet communication and social network with pushing, entertaining and interesting information about environmental products.

XVI. CONCLUSION:

Green marketing includes a huge than a company’s marketing asserts. If firms are willingly bearing the responsibilities for environmental degradation it should not be handled only by them. Green marketing explains that a consumer is ready to pay for all those products which are eco-friendly and does not harms them. With the great impact of global warming reaching large, it is very crucial that green marketing should be treated as the norm instead of an exception. Reclaiming of metals, paper, plastics etc., in a secure and environmentally harmless mode should become much more structured and universal. It is the lesson not to be forgotten that the industrial buyer also has the power to pressurize suppliers to amend their activities. Therefore, an environmental committed firms may not only construct goods that have decreased their injurious impression on the environment, they may also be able to stimulate their suppliers to behave in a more environmentally “responsible” vogue.

Green marketing never be treated only as marketing approach tool, but has to be recognized as much greater strength, as it has social and environmental extents to it. Therefore, green marketing considers

even more likelihoods and relevance in developing countries like India.

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